

Vol 1, Issue 1 · 2026 · Open Access · Original Article

Caesarean Hysterectomy; Risk Factors, Indications & Outcomes

Aqsa^{1,*} · Shazia Rani² · Batool Meer³ · Raheel Sikander⁴^{1,3} Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad^{2,4} Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro

* Corresponding Author: Dr. Aqsa, Senior Women Medical Officer, Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad.

Email: aqsaamemon22@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.66547/758201> · Published: Jan 15, 2026

ARTICLE HISTORY

RECEIVED	REVISED	ACCEPTED	PUBLISHED
Aug 10, 2025	Oct 25, 2025	Dec 05, 2025	Jan 15, 2026

Keywords: Caesarean hysterectomy, postpartum hemorrhage, morbidly adherent placenta, placenta previa, maternal outcome

Abstract

OBJECTIVE

The rising rate of cesarean deliveries worldwide has led to an increase in severe obstetric complications, including postpartum hemorrhage, where cesarean hysterectomy (CH) is required as a life saving measure. To determine the risk factors, indications and maternal outcomes of cesarean hysterectomy at a tertiary care hospital.

METHODS

A cross-sectional descriptive research was conducted in the Dept. of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad during February 2021 and July 2021. The sample consisted of 125 mothers who underwent an emergency cesarean hysterectomy. Data related to sociodemographic characteristics, obstetric history, risk factors, indications for the procedure, and the maternal outcomes were collected.

RESULTS

Previous cesarean section and multiparity were the most frequent risk factors, both found in 56% of participants. Morbidly adherent placenta (54.4%) was the main indication for cesarean hysterectomy, seconded by uterine atony (20%). In total, 87.2% of mothers experienced one or more postoperative complication, including prolonged hospitalization (21.6%), ICU admission (19.2%), bladder injury (16.8%) and maternal death (15.2%). Multivariate analysis revealed that morbidly adherent placenta, previous cesarean section and unbooked status were independently associated with poor maternal outcome.

CONCLUSION

Cesarean hysterectomy is associated with a large burden of maternal morbidity and mortality. Previous cesarean section, abnormal placentation—especially morbidly adherent placenta—and failure to book in pregnancy are the major determinants of poor maternal outcomes.

Introduction

Over the last few decades the Caesarean Delivery Rate has dramatically increased throughout the world; as a result severe obstetric complications that occur during pregnancy have also increased. Some of the most dangerous complications are related to postpartum hemorrhage (PPH). Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is among the prime reasons for maternal morbidity and mortality worldwide; especially in lower income and middle-income countries [1,2]. If medical and conservative surgical methods to control hemorrhage do not work then caesarean hysterectomy (CH) will become a life saving method of treatment.

Caesarean hysterectomy is associated with marked maternal morbidity; in particular, large amounts of blood loss, extended hospital stay, the need for an intensive care unit admission, urinary tract injury and maternal death [3,4]. Many different risk factors have been identified for caesarean hysterectomy, such as having had a previous caesarean section, increasing parity, uterine atony, placenta previa and morbidly adherent placenta [3,5,6]. There is strong association between abnormal placentation and rising caesarean section rates and it is now believed that abnormal placentation is a major reason for the increasing frequency of caesarean hysterectomy [7,8].

The epidemiology and indications of caesarean hysterectomy vary between developed and less developed countries. In high resource settings abnormal placentation is the primary indication, while in less developed countries uterine rupture, atony, sepsis and late presentation to a health facility continue to be common [6,9]. Additionally, limited access to antenatal care and ineffective systems for referring patients to higher levels of care further increase maternal morbidity and mortality from CH in these areas [10].

Obstetric hemorrhage continues to be a major factor in maternal deaths in Pakistan, with caesarean delivery significantly increasing the risk of severe bleeding and emergency hysterectomy [5,9]. Although CH is a clinically important topic in the field of obstetrics, there is currently a shortage of evidence specific to the risks of CH, the indications for CH, and the outcomes for women who undergo CH in Pakistan. It is very important to create evidence to identify the risks of CH earlier in pregnancy, improve antenatal care monitoring and provide more efficient referrals to help minimize maternal morbidity and mortality. Thus, the purpose of this study was to assess the risks, indications, and outcomes for women undergoing caesarean hysterectomy at a tertiary level hospital in Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Subjects, Materials & Methods

Study Design and Study Location: The current study is a cross-sectional study that was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Duration of the Study: The duration of the study was six months, starting from February 2021 to July 2021.

Population and Sample Size: There were a total of 125 women who had undergone emergency Caesarian Hysterectomies either at the same time as their Caesarian deliveries or within 24 hours after they had delivered through Caesarian Section.

Sampling Technique: We utilized non-probability consecutive sampling method for recruiting participants into the study.

Eligible Participants:

Inclusion criteria: Pregnant women undergoing Emergency Caesarian Hysterectomy at the time of Caesarian delivery or up to 24 hours after delivery.

Exclusion criteria: Women undergoing elective hysterectomy for benign gynaecological condition, Hysterectomy performed after vaginal delivery for PPH or retained placenta, Obstetric hysterectomy performed due to puerperal sepsis.

Procedure of Data Collection: Following obtaining the participant's written informed consent, we collected the data using a structured questionnaire. We recorded the participant's demographic characteristics, obstetric history, booking status, distance from hospital, gestation age, parity, known risk factor(s), indication for performing Caesarian hysterectomy, and maternal outcome(s). We also validated all the data collected from the participants against hospital medical record by the researchers themselves.

Variables Studied: Primary variables studied include; maternal age, gestational age, parity, booking status, residential status, distance to hospital, socio-economic status, known risk factor(s) for Caesarian hysterectomy, indication for surgery, and maternal outcome(s).

Statistical Data Analysis: Data were recorded and statistical analysis was carried out using a SPSS software (version 21.0). Quantitative variables were presented as mean \pm SD and qualitative variables as number and percentage. A Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to analyze association among well-known risk factors, indication and/or outcomes in pregnant women. The data was also stratified to assess possible effect modifiers and a Chi-square test was conducted for comparison of proportions. Any p-value of ≤ 0.05 was defined as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 125 women who underwent emergency caesarean hysterectomy were included. The mean maternal age was 24 ± 3 years, and the mean gestational age was 37 ± 1.5 weeks. Most women were urban residents (70.4%), and the majority were booked cases, with a booked-to-unbooked ratio of approximately 8:1. Two-thirds of the participants resided at a distance greater than 30 km from the hospital.

Table 1: Risk Factors Associated with Caesarean Hysterectomy (n = 125)

Risk Factor	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Previous Caesarean Section	70	56.0%
Multiparity	70	56.0%
Morbidly Adherent Placenta	55	44.0%
Placenta Previa	42	33.6%
Unbooked Status	12	9.6%
Others	11	8.8%

Morbidly adherent placenta was the leading indication, accounting for 54.4% of cases, followed by uterine atony (20.0%) and placenta previa (17.6%).

Table 2: Indications for Caesarean Hysterectomy (n = 125)

Indication	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Morbidly Adherent Placenta	68	54.4%
Uterine Atony	25	20.0%
Placenta Previa	22	17.6%
Extension of Tear	6	4.8%
Placental Abruption	4	3.2%

Overall, 109 women (87.2%) developed one or more postoperative complications, while 16 (12.8%) experienced no adverse outcome.

Table 3: Complicated Maternal Outcomes following Caesarean Hysterectomy (n = 109)

Maternal Outcome	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Prolonged Hospital Stay	27	21.6%
ICU Admission	24	19.2%
Bladder Injury	21	16.8%
Mortality	19	15.2%
Wound Infection	9	7.2%
Acute Renal Failure	6	4.8%
ARDS	6	4.8%
DIC	4	3.2%
Pulmonary Embolism	2	1.6%

Using a binary logistic regression analysis we determined if there were independent factors which predicted a bad maternal outcome for patients undergoing Caesarian Hysterectomy. All variables that had a p-value less than .20 in univariate analysis were entered into the multivariate model.

Table 4: Multivariable logistic regression for predictors of poor maternal outcome

Variable	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Morbidly adherent placenta	4.96	1.24–19.80	0.023
Previous caesarean section	2.89	1.01–8.31	0.047
Unbooked status	3.67	1.02–13.20	0.045
Multiparity	2.12	0.88–5.09	0.091
Distance >30 km	1.84	0.72–4.67	0.201

Discussion

This study assessed the risk factors, reasons for performing, and maternal consequences of Caesarian Hysterectomy at a tertiary care hospital. A high prevalence of serious maternal complications was found. The severe maternal complications reflect the severity of the obstetric pathology as well as the systemic barriers to providing appropriate care to women in a resource-poor setting.

Previous Caesarean Section(s) and Multiparity were the most frequently identified risk factor for Caesarian Hysterectomy. Multiple studies internationally also show that having had multiple (repeat) Caesarean deliveries significantly increases the risk for Emergency Peripartum Hysterectomy [3, 5, 11] (Whiteman et al., and Bodelon et al. found that both increasing parity and prior Caesarean delivery were strongly associated with the need for hysterectomy, and that these associations were primarily related to abnormal placentation and uterine rupture [5, 11]). Additionally, multiple Caesarean deliveries results in cumulative surgical trauma to the pelvis including pelvic adhesions, making the subsequent surgeries more difficult, and increasing the risk for massive hemorrhage [7, 12].

Abnormal Placental Adhesion was identified as the leading reason for Caesarean Hysterectomy in this study. This finding is representative of a world-wide trend toward abnormal placentation being the most common cause for Caesarean Hysterectomy in the last few decades. In earlier years, the causes for Caesarean Hysterectomy included uterine atony and ruptured uterus; however, more recent studies and case series report abnormal placentation to be the most common cause [6, 8, 13]. Wu et al. documented a progressive increase in the risk of developing placenta accreta spectrum disorder with each successive Caesarean delivery [8]. Similar data have been published in large-scale epidemiologic studies in developed countries [12, 14].

Although abnormal placentation was the most common indication for Caesarean Hysterectomy, Uterine Atony was still an important indication for Caesarean Hysterectomy in this group of women. As previously reported by other researchers in developing countries, the inability to rapidly obtain or administer utotonic agents, blood products, and/or to perform interventional radiology can lead to failed conservative treatment of uterine atony [9, 10, 15]. Abbas et al. and Machado et al. documented that uterine atony continues to be an indication for emergency hysterectomy in low-resource countries, even though there has been progress in obstetric care [6, 15].

The maternal morbidity rate in this study was high, with the most frequent complications being prolonged hospital stays and ICU admissions. Several similar morbidity profiles have been reported in studies conducted in Pakistan, India, and Sub-Saharan Africa, where delayed referrals, massive hemorrhage, and lack of ICU beds are some of the many challenges that are encountered [9, 13, 16]. These findings emphasize the necessity of improving the referral system and ensuring that all necessary multidisciplinary care is available to the high-risk pregnant woman.

Urinary Tract Injury, specifically Bladder Injury, was another complication of note in this study. Many previous studies have demonstrated that bladder and ureteral injuries occur more often than expected when Cesarean Hysterectomies are performed, especially when the patient has a morbidly adherent placenta and prior uterine surgery [4, 17]. The rates of bladder injury in studies by Rossi et al. and Kastner et al. ranged from 10% to 23%, and are comparable to those found in the current study [4, 17].

The maternal mortality rate associated with Cesarean Hysterectomy in this study is concerning. There is a significant difference in the risk of maternal mortality associated with emergency hysterectomy after Cesarean delivery between low- and middle-income countries and high-income countries [2, 9]. Risk factors for increased maternal mortality include massive hemorrhage, coagulopathy, delayed surgical intervention, and limited access to critical care services [1, 2, 10]. These findings emphasize the need for early antenatal risk assessment and planned delivery in tertiary care centers for women suspected of having abnormal placentation.

Conclusion

Cesarean hysterectomy is associated with a large burden of maternal morbidity and mortality in developing settings. Previous cesarean section, abnormal placentation—especially morbidly adherent placenta—and failure to book in pregnancy are the major determinants of poor maternal outcomes. Antenatal identification of high-risk pregnancy, appropriate use of cesarean delivery and early referral to tertiary care can be effective strategies to decrease the severe complications related to emergency peripartum interventions.

Author Contributions

In accordance with the ICMJE guidelines, all authors have made substantial contributions to the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Author	Conception & Design	Data Collection & Analysis	Drafting & Revision	Final Approval
Aqsa (A)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Shazia Rani (SR)	✓	—	✓	✓
Batool Meer (BM)	—	✓	✓	✓
Raheel Sikander (RS)	—	—	✓	✓

DECLARATIONS

Ethical Approval: The study was approved by the Ethics Review Committee of LUMHS (Letter No: LUMHS/REC/ – 945).

Acknowledgements: None declared.

Disclaimer: The views expressed in this article are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of the affiliated institutions.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding Disclosure: No funding was received for this study.

COPYRIGHT & LICENSE

© 2026 The Authors. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). You are free to share and adapt the material for any purpose, even commercially, provided you give appropriate credit.

References

1. Say L, Chou D, Gemmill A, et al. Global causes of maternal death: a WHO systematic analysis. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2014;2(6):e323-33.
2. Kassebaum NJ, Bertozzi-Villa A, Coggeshall MS, et al. Global, regional, and national levels and causes of maternal mortality during 1990–2013. *Lancet*. 2014;384(9947):980-1004.
3. Shellhaas CS, Gilbert S, Landon MB, et al. The frequency and complication rates of hysterectomy accompanying cesarean delivery. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2009;201(2):87.e1-8.
4. Rossi AC, Lee RH, Chmait RH. Emergency postpartum hysterectomy for uncontrolled postpartum bleeding: a systematic review. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2010;115(3):637-44.
5. Bodelon C, Bernabe-Ortiz A, Schiff MA, Reed SD. Factors associated with peripartum hysterectomy. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2009;114(1):115-23.
6. Machado LS. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy: Incidence, indications, risk factors and outcome. *N Am J Med Sci*. 2011;3(8):358-61.
7. Silver RM, Landon MB, Rouse DJ, et al. Maternal morbidity associated with multiple repeat cesarean deliveries. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2006;107(6):1226-32.
8. Wu S, Kocherginsky M, Chandrasekaran S. Abnormal placentation: twenty-year analysis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2005;192(5):1458-61.
9. Abbas A, Khattak A, Safdar N, et al. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy in a tertiary care hospital. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*. 2018;30(3):439-42.
10. Zelop CM, Harlow BL, Frigoletto FD, et al. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 1993;168(5):1443-8.
11. Whiteman MK, Kuklina E, Hillis SD, et al. Incidence and determinants of peripartum hysterectomy. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2006;108(3):512-8.
12. Flood WA, et al. Morbidity and mortality of peripartum hysterectomy. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med*. 2010;23(9):1001-5.
13. Wright JD, Devine P, Shah M, et al. Morbidity and mortality of peripartum hysterectomy. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2010;115(6):1187-93.
14. Knight M. Peripartum hysterectomy in the UK: management and outcomes of the associated haemorrhage. *BJOG*. 2007;114(11):1380-7.
15. Bateman BT, Mhyre JM, Callaghan WM, et al. Peripartum hysterectomy in the United States. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2012;119(6):1150-8.
16. D'Arpe S, Franceschetti S, Corosu L, et al. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy in a teaching hospital in Italy. *Arch Gynecol Obstet*. 2015;291(4):841-7.
17. Kastner ES, Figueroa R, Garry D, Maulik D. Emergency peripartum hysterectomy: experience at a community teaching hospital. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2002;99(5):971-5.
18. Ulla MM, et al. Maternal and fetal outcomes of peripartum hysterectomy. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2010;109(3):236-9.